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RESULTS**

"Sana All" Expression: A Sociopragmatic Analysis

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the sociopragmatic aspects of the Filipino expression "Sana All" analyzing its usage, interpretations, and functions within a secondary school context. Through qualitative design, the research explored (1) the various situations in which the "Sana All" expression is used and encountered; (2) how learners, teachers, and non-teaching personnel interpret its meaning in their daily interactions; (3) variations in its usage across these groups; and (4) its sociopragmatic functions.

Findings revealed that "Sana All" is commonly employed in casual conversations, social media interactions, and situations involving admiration for others' possessions, achievements, or romantic life, as well as during self-reflection. Interpretations ranged from hopeful aspiration and playful envy to admiration and a call for fairness. While students primarily used it to express admiration or dissatisfaction, teachers and non-teaching staff extended its use to romantic contexts. The study identified its sociopragmatic functions as complimenting, congratulating, and complaining, aligning with Searle and Vanderveken's (1985) expressive illocutionary acts.

Recommendations included integrating "Sana All" into language lessons, conducting further linguistic analyses, and adopting the proposed discourse framework for effective communication. This research contributes to understanding contemporary Filipino expressions in sociopragmatic contexts.

Keywords: *Sana All, sociopragmatics, expressive illocutionary acts, Filipino expressions, language usage*

INTRODUCTION

Language in communication is increasingly complex, evolving from day-to-day interaction to dynamic educational and social contexts. Pragmatics, the study of language use in context, is crucial for understanding how meaning is conveyed and interpreted beyond literal definitions (Thomas, 1983). Within this field, sociopragmatics examines the intersection of language with social perceptions, norms, and cultural factors (Haugh et al., 2021). It focuses on how variables like age, gender, and social setting influence communicative acts.

The rise of social media has accelerated the creation and adoption of new linguistic expressions. A prominent example in the Philippines is "Sana All," a phrase coined from the Filipino word 'sana' (hope/wish) and the English word 'all'. Traditionally seen as a call for equality, it has been popularized as a catchphrase to wish for an individual's good fortune (Vincentino et al., 2022). While Pontillas et al. (2020) identified "Sana All" as a potential barrier to communication due to its indirectness, a comprehensive analysis of its sociopragmatic aspects remains underexplored.

This study bridges this gap by investigating the "Sana All" expression within the specific social context of a secondary school. Guided by Speech Act Theory (Austin, 1962; Searle, 1969), Social Identity Theory (Tajfel & Turner, 1979), and Politeness Theory (Brown & Levinson, 1978), this research seeks to understand how this expression functions as a social and communicative tool. Specifically, this study aims to answer the following questions: What are the various situations in which the "Sana All" expression is used and encountered? How do learners, teachers, and non-teaching personnel

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interpret its meaning? How does its usage vary among these three groups? What are its sociopragmatic functions within the secondary school context?

METHODS

This study employed a qualitative research design, specifically a phenomenological approach, to explore the lived experiences and perceptions of the participants regarding the "Sana All" expression. This approach is suited to understanding how individuals produce and interpret meaning in their everyday interactions (Searle, 1983). The study was conducted at Federico A. Estipona Memorial High School. Using purposive sampling, 30 participants were selected, comprising three distinct groups: 10 Learners (Junior and Senior High School students), 10 Teachers, and 10 Non-Teaching Personnel. Written informed consent was secured from all participants prior to data collection.

The primary instrument for data collection was a semi-structured interview guide containing four key questions. The questions probed into specific situations of use, common contexts, personal meanings, and interpretations of the "Sana All" expression. Face-to-face interviews were conducted, audio-recorded, and transcribed verbatim.

Data analysis followed a dual approach. First, thematic analysis was used to identify, analyze, and report patterns (themes) across the dataset, addressing the situations, interpretations, and usage of the expression. Second, sociopragmatic analysis was employed, drawing on Speech Act Theory (Austin, 1962; Searle, 1969), to analyze the linguistic data and determine the illocutionary forces and social functions of "Sana All" in conversation.

The interview guide was validated by experts in English Language Education, demonstrating a Content Validity Index (CVI) of 9.0 and good internal consistency reliability (ICR = 0.87). Rigorous transcription and a dual-analytical approach enhanced the trustworthiness and credibility of the findings.

RESULTS

The analysis identified six primary situations where "Sana All" is used: 1) during informal settings where the expression is used during casual conversations, recess, and bonding with friends, family, and classmates; 2) when admiring others' material possessions (e.g., new bags, shoes), physical appearance, or lifestyle; 3) when posting on social media like comments on posts about achievements, meals, or travel; 4) when giving comments on academic or professional growth or achievement such as peers' high grades, contest wins, or colleagues' promotions; 5) when giving comment on others' relationships, receiving gifts on Valentine's Day, or marriage proposals; and 6) when expressing dissatisfaction when comparing one's own situation (e.g., workload) to that of others.

Participants' interpretations of "Sana All" fell into five themes: 1) hope or wish, the dominant interpretation, meaning a desire to possess or experience what others have; 2) envy, often described as "playful envy" or lighthearted jealousy; 3) admiration or aspiration, meaning a form of admiration that inspires a desire to achieve similar things; 4) playful jab, used as a humorous or sarcastic remark during gossip or casual banter; and 5) equality or fairness, where in some contexts, it was interpreted as a commentary on social inequality and a call for fairness.

Students primarily used "Sana All" to express admiration for material possessions, academic success, and to complain about unfair workloads or their own perceived lack of productivity, while teachers and non-teaching personnel also used it for admiration and congratulatory purposes but extended its application to contexts of professional promotion and, notably, romantic relationships—a usage not prominent among students.

The analysis, grounded in Speech Act Theory, revealed that "Sana All" primarily functions as an expressive illocutionary act. Its sociopragmatic functions are: 1) Complimenting when used to express admiration for another's material possessions, physical appearance, or lifestyle (e.g., "Sana All" on a new dress); 2) Congratulating when used to express admiration for another's academic achievements, professional success, or romantic milestones (e.g., "Sana All" on winning a contest); 3) Complaining when used to express dissatisfaction or frustration, often through self-comparison (e.g., "Sana All" to peers who are not required to do a project).

DISCUSSION

This study demonstrates that the "Sana All" expression is a complex sociopragmatic tool rather than a simple statement of hope. Its functionality as an expressive speech act (Searle & Vanderveken, 1985) allows speakers to manage social relationships by conveying nuanced attitudes—from solidarity and admiration to subtle complaint—in a culturally acceptable, indirect manner.

The variation in usage between students and staff highlights the role of Social Identity Theory. For students, it reinforces peer group dynamics, while for adults, it navigates more complex social hierarchies involving career and personal life. The expression's indirectness also aligns with Politeness Theory (Brown & Levinson, 1978), as it allows speakers to express envy or dissatisfaction without performing a direct face-threatening act, thereby maintaining social harmony.

The finding that "Sana All" can function as a complaint challenges a purely surface-level interpretation of the phrase. This aligns with Vincentino et al. (2022), who noted its use to highlight privilege and inequality, showing its capacity to convey social commentary.

The findings suggest that language education should integrate contemporary expressions like "Sana All" to teach pragmatic competence. Understanding its various functions can help students and educators decode indirect meanings and communicate more effectively across different contexts. However, this study was limited to one secondary school. Future research could employ a quantitative or corpus-based approach to examine its usage across different regions and age demographics in the Philippines. Further analysis could also explore its semantic and syntactic properties in greater depth.

CONCLUSION

The "Sana All" expression is a multifaceted element of modern Filipino communication. Its meaning is not fixed but is dynamically constructed in interaction, serving the key sociopragmatic functions of complimenting, congratulating, and complaining. This study confirms that "Sana All" is a rich linguistic resource that reflects shared aspirations, social dynamics, and cultural values within a learning community. Acknowledging and understanding such expressions is vital for fostering effective and empathetic communication in evolving educational landscapes.

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